

IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL TRAINING OF FREESTYLE WRESTLERS.

Yakupbaev A.A.

Teacher of the Nukus branch of the Uzbek State
University of Physical Education and Sports, Uzbekistan, Nukus
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10590667>

Annotation: This article discusses the physical training of freestyle wrestlers. A set of exercises has been developed for the development of general and special physical training of freestyle wrestlers.

Key words: Freestyle wrestling, training load, physical training, complex exercise.

In the rapidly growing trend in the development of world sports, the role of freestyle wrestling is also increasing. In particular, the share of men in the growth dynamics of those involved in freestyle wrestling is constantly increasing. This, in turn, places high demands on their preparation. These processes require the development of improved methods based on new approaches to training wrestlers. One of the important tasks is the physical training of wrestlers. Systematic reforms are being carried out with all types of sports in our republic to further develop wrestling and increase the number of people involved in this sport. In particular, tasks have been set to carry out organizational, practical and propaganda work to attract freestyle wrestling to classes and their becoming professional athletes. In freestyle wrestling, physical training is of particular importance, which is one of the important factors in improving the skills and special indicators of wrestlers. The problem of rationalizing the means and methods of physical training for athletes is constantly in the attention of scientists and practitioners (Verkhoshansky Yu. 1988, G.S. Tumanyan 2009). Recently, a number of aspects have been updated regarding the optimal ratio of loads in different directions, the sequence of their inclusion in physical training freestyle wrestlers of various skill levels and training.

Purpose of the study: Improving the physical training of 16-17 year old qualified freestyle wrestlers in different weight categories at the stage of sports improvement.

Research methods:

Literature analysis;
Pedagogical supervision;
Theoretical analysis;
Experimental evaluation;
Pedagogical experiment-test;
Math statistics;

Research results and discussion. It is known that the physical training of freestyle wrestlers is important for achieving high results. However, in strength training, it is advisable to use a properly selected training load so that the wrestlers' muscles are not only adapted to the load, but also have high speed. To improve the physical training of wrestlers, we proposed a set of control exercises.

Research results and discussion. It is known that the physical training of freestyle wrestlers is important for achieving high results. However, in strength training, it is advisable to use a properly selected training load so that the wrestlers' muscles are not only adapted to the load, but also have high speed. To improve the physical training of wrestlers, we proposed a set of control exercises.

The first mesocycle is training sessions with weights, starting with the preparation of the athlete's body weight. When working with a barbell, the weight and number of repetitions vary to a certain extent. Optimal repetitions are minimal when performing exercises with heavy weights. While performing exercises, it is important to hold your body correctly and breathe. Recommended weights are needed to increase muscle strength. And repeated exercises with light weights have little effect on muscle irritants.

ORGANIZATION OF THE STUDY

A pedagogical experiment was conducted based on the training plan we developed with the participation of freestyle wrestlers (16-17-year-old boys) from the republican sports school (Nukus) specialized in individual wrestling. In the pedagogical experiment, 10 athletes participated in experimental groups. Through the comparative analysis of the initial and final indicators of participants in the research, the strength efficiency of volleyball players in the competition was based. 10 athletes from experimental groups took part in the pedagogical experiment. Through a comparative analysis of the initial and final indicators of the study participants, the physical training of freestyle wrestlers was substantiated.

To assess the level of development of physical fitness, the most important control standards were used: Running for 100 meters (s), pull-up on the horizontal bar 20 sek, push-ups 20 sek, jump from the standing position to the length (sm), shuttle run 4×10 м (sek), how to hip toss, shoulder throw.

At the beginning and end of the experiment, an experimental group of freestyle wrestlers in sports improvement groups.

№	Physical fitness indicators	Before the experiment			After the experiment		
		X	σ	V%	X	σ	V%
1	Running for 100 meters (s)	13	0,2	1,8	12,4	0,2	2,2
2	Pull-up on the horizontal bar 20 sek	8,4	1,07	12,7	10,5	0,97	8,4
3	Push-ups 20 sek	12,5	1,08	6,9	13,8	1,03	5,8
4	Jump from the standing position to the length (sm)	211,2	6,4	3,03	217	4,6	2,1
5	Shuttle run 4×10 м (sek)	6.9	0.7	10.4	6.7	0.5	8.95

6	How to hip toss	10	0,9	9,4	11,6	0,5	4,4
7	Shoulder Throw	11	0,8	7,4	12,5	0,8	6,6

Figure 1. Results of the experiment before and after the experiment of freestyle wrestlers

As can be seen from the tables, before and after the experiment of the experimental group, the physical fitness indicators of freestyle wrestlers increased significantly: Before the experiment, running 100 meters average value 13 seconds after the experiment the average value improved by 12.4 seconds, before the experiment pull-ups on the horizontal bar 20 seconds average value 8.4 after the experiment the average value improved by 10.5, before the experiment push-ups 20 seconds average value 12.5 after the experiment the average value improved by 13.8, before the experiment standing long jump (cm) average value 211.2 after the experiment the average value improved by 217, before the experiment shuttle run 4x10 m (sec) average value 6.9 after the experiment the average value improved by 6.7, before the experiment hip throw average value 10 after the experiment average value improved by 11.6, before the experiment shoulder throw average value 11 after the experiment the average improved by 11.5.

Conclusion: In conclusion, we can say that the special performance of the body has a positive effect on increasing physical fitness due to the correct use of a set of exercises and training loads of freestyle wrestlers at the stage of sports improvement.

References:

1. Alimbaevich, Y. A., & Mukhtarovna, A. D. (2022). Influence of Free Wrestling on Physical Student Development in Karakalpakstan. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 7, 93-95.
2. Жарылкапов, У. Б. (2023). КУРАШЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ВА ТАКТИК ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. Fan-Sportga, (2), 110-111.

3. Baxadirovich, J. U., Polatovich, Q. R., & Koptileovich, T. M. (2022). Peculiarities of planning freestyle wrestling training sessions. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5, 59-62.
4. Жарылкапов, У. Б., & Алимбетова, А. (2022). ЭЛЕМЕНТЫ ГРЕКО-РИМСКОЙ БОРЬБЫ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ФИЗИЧЕСКОМУ ВОСПИТАНИЮ. In Развитие отраслей АПК на основе формирования эффективного механизма хозяйствования (pp. 530-532).
5. Жарылкапов, У. Б., & Жолдасов, А. (2022). ТАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ПОДГОТОВКА БОРЦОВ ЖЕНЩИН. In Развитие отраслей АПК на основе формирования эффективного механизма хозяйствования (pp. 532-534).
6. Jarilkarov, U. B., Qaljanov, R. P., & Tolibaeva, D. K. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF JUMPING ABILITY IN VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS BY MEANS WEIGHTLIFTING STRENGTH EXERCISES. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 4(01), 74-80.
7. Alimbaevich, Y. A., & Mukhtarovna, A. D. (2022). Influence of Free Wrestling on Physical Student Development in Karakalpakistan. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 7, 93-95.
8. Primbetov, A. (2023). THE USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S WRESTLING. *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 2(1), 196-201.
9. Auesbaevich, P. A. (2020, August). IMPROVING THE PROCESS OF TRAINING FOR ACTIVITY ACCORDING TO THE CHARACTERISTICS OF KURASH. In The 8 th International scientific and practical conference—Eurasian scientific congress|(August 9-11, 2020) Barca Academy Publishing, Barcelona, Spain. 2020. 370 p (p. 178).
10. Primbetov, A. (2023). THE USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S WRESTLING. *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 2(1), 196-201.
11. Ayesbaevich, P. A. (2023). WAYS TO DEVELOP WOMEN'S PHYSICAL FITNESS IN FREESTYLE WRESTLING. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 247-252.
12. Ayesbaevich, P. A. (2023). TOOK THE RACE PREPARATION AND PLANNING IT. *Open Access Repository*, 4(03), 25-27.
13. Auyesbayevich, P. A. (2023). INJURY PREVENTION AND RECOVERY STRATEGIES FOR HIGH-LEVEL FEMALE FREESTYLE WRESTLERS. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 21, 61-65.
14. Auyesbayevich, P. A. (2023, November). THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN ENHANCING TRAINING AND TECHNIQUE IN WOMEN'S FREESTYLE WRESTLING. In E Conference Zone (pp. 1-7).
15. Тойлибаев, С. М. (2019). Некоторые особенности профессиональной деятельности студентов факультетов физической культуры. In Современные векторы развития образования: актуальные проблемы и перспективные решения (pp. 148-150).
16. Кузнецова, Е. Т., Турдымуратов, Ж. А., & Тойлибаев, С. М. (2022). Организация стажировок как одна из важных составляющих дополнительного образования преподавателей.
17. Тойлибаев, С. М. (2023). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОСНОВНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ УНИВЕРСИТЕТОВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА. In Проблемы и перспективы развития спортивного образования, науки и практики (pp. 241-245).

18. Тойлибаев, С. М. (2021). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ ОСНОВНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ В СТАНОВЛЕНИИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ. In Проблемы и перспективы развития спортивного образования, науки и практики (pp. 334-337).

